

THE EFFECTS OF AUSTEMPERING TIME AND DIFFERENT QUENCHING MEDIA ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CAMSHAFT

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Keywords: Camshaft, Casting, Austenitizing, Austempering, Mechanical Properties, Microstructure

Abstract

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of austempering time and different quenching media on the mechanical and microstructure properties of the camshafts made of ductile cast iron (GGG80). For this purpose, optimum casting conditions were determined with NOVACAST program, the camshafts were produced by using the sand casting method. The casting was carried out at 1425°C and the pouring time was in 14 sec. For nodulizing process, Fe-Si-Mg alloy has been used and Fe-Si-Ba-Ca-Al alloy has been for inoculation process. The produced camshaft was subjected to the austenitizing process (90 minutes at 900°C under vacuum furnace). The camshaft was then transferred to a salt bath (50%KNO₃+50%NaNO₃) at 260°C and austempering was applied for 60-120-240-360 min. The camshafts that completed the austempering process were allowed to cool down in different quenching media (oil and air). The microstructure of the camshafts were examined under an optical microscope and mechanical tests (hardness, tensile and wear tests) were performed. In this study, the highest hardness and wear strengths value was observed in the camshafts that were austempered at 120 minutes and cooled down in the oil. The highest tensile strength was observed in the camshafts that were austempered at 120 minutes and cooled down in the air.

1. Introduction

The production of camshafts used in engines, it is carried out with the casting and machining techniques. Today, camshafts are produced from gray, nodular graphite cast iron, because of many advantages, and also machining of steel [1-2].

Spheroidal graphite cast iron has properties “such as high tensile strength, high ductility, high wear resistance, low melting temperature and easy production at low cost [3-5].

Austempering heat treatment may be implemented to spherical graphite cast iron. When researches on austempered spheroidal graphite cast iron increase, the field of its use increase also. Austempered spherical graphite cast irons have been started to be used instead of casting or forging steels used in the automotive industry [6-7].

When the thickness of the cross section of spherical graphite cast iron increases, it is difficult to produce

good quality of castings suitable for austempering. As the increase in cross-sectional thickness causes a decrease in the cooling rate, the number of graphite sphere decreases and micro-shrinkage, porosity, and deterioration of graphite sphericity and eutectic carburetion and segregation of alloying elements such as Mn and Mo may occur [8].

The spherical graphite cast iron should contain high amounts of alloying elements for the application of a complete austempering process. Higher amounts of alloying elements increase the possibility of segregation [9].

After heat treatments, oil-based coolant and room-temperature air environment are used. It has been observed that residual stresses in the chilled parts of the oil are higher than those of the heat treated parts in order to determine the effects of different cooling media [10].

The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of austempering and different quenching media on microstructure and mechanical properties of heavy vehicles camshaft.

2. Experimental Method

2.1. Materials and Methods

In order to eliminate possible errors, the liquid metal filling (Fig. 1a) and shrinkage vacuum) with the runners and feeders (Fig. 1b) were simulated by 3D solid modeling of sand casting models in the Nova Cast casting simulation program, before the production of ductile iron camshaft.

Figure 1. Casting simulation; a) liquid phase, b) shrinkage

Mould sand that will be used in the camshaft casting was prepared. Melting of the metal in three different chemical analyzes was conducted in induction furnaces. The chemical composition was analyzed by spectrometer and Atas thermal analysis equipment. Table 1 shows the chemical compositions of cast iron used in camshaft production.

Table 1. Chemical analyses of casting camshaft

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Mg	Cr	Ni	Mo
3,61	2,45	0,27	0,034	0,024	0,045	0,077	0,061	0,023
Cu	Al	Ti	V	Nb	W	Co	Sn	Fe
0,051	0,005	0,01	0,005	0,002	0,003	0,001	0,003	Balance

Nodulizing process was done in the treatment crucible between temperature of 1550-1570°C and Fe-Si-Mg alloy was used for nodulizing treatment. While liquid metal was poured into casting crucible, inoculation process was done by adding Fe-Si-Ba-Ca-Al alloy. Casting process was completed 15 sec. and at the temperature of about 1430°C by controlling laser type thermocouple. By this way, camshaft and tensile samples (Y blocks) were casted by sand mold casting method.

Remaining sands on the surface of camshafts and Y blocks has been cleaned by sand blasting device. The runners and risers of camshafts and Y blocks were separated by cutting and their surfaces were ground on CNC machines. Tensile test samples were produced from Y blocks according to ASTM A597 standard (Figure 2).

Figure 2. ASTM A597 standard tensile sample 2D technical drawings

2.2. Heat Treatment

In the austempering heat treatments, cabin type furnace is used that works with electrical resistance and can go up to 1150°C and has atmosphere and temperature control. After the camshafts were austenitized at 900°C, 90 minutes, austempered rapidly in salt bath (%50KNO₃+%50NaNO₃) at 260°C, 60-120-240-360 minutes duration. After that, camshafts were cooled in air and in oil to room temperature.

2.3. Metallographic Process

Heat treated camshafts samples were made ready for microstructure investigation by standard metallographic methods (mounting, grinding, polishing) and then etching process was conducted to the samples by using 2% nital solution. Microstructure of the camshaft was examined under a Nikon MA200 optical microscopy and analyzed by Clemex Vision Lite of image analysis software. % of nodularity, nodule size and number, % volume graphite, ferrite and pearlite were measured.

2.4. Mechanical Tests

2.4.1. Hardness Test

Hardness of core sections on camshafts as casted and austempered conditions were measured applying 750kgf load in terms of brinell hardness by Instron Wolpert hardness device. Hardness test was measured five times from different sections.

2.4.2. Tensile Test

Tensile test machine called ALSA with 20 tons was used for tension test. Tensile strength, yield strength and the amount of % elongation were determined. Tension test were conducted three times and average values of tensile properties were given and then the fracture surfaces of each sample were examined by SEM.

2.4.3. Wear Test

For wear tests, wear test sample were prepared by taking cut views from cam sections on the camshafts under casted and heat treated conditions. UTS T10/20 brand pin-on disc type test apparatus (tribometer) was used for wear test. Wear test was conducted in accordance with ASTM Standard G99-05, with various loads, constant distance and at a constant RPM. Then, weight loss was measured by sensitive balance and wear surfaces were examined by optical microscope either on sample or on ball bearing that is wear counterpart. Because of ASTM G99-05 standard is based on the measurement of wear volume, wear on ball bearing was calculated by using mathematical relationship and direct measuring volumetric loss. Wear test parameters used in this study are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Wear test parameters

Test Parameters	Test 1	Test 2
Wear ball bearing	100Cr6	100Cr6
Ball Bearing hardness (HRC)	65	65
Ball bearing diameter (mm)	5	5
Nominal Load (N)	30	30
Disc Rotating Speed (rpm)	300	300
Sliding speed (m/s)	0,095	0,095
Sliding distance (m)	500	500
Test temperature (°C)	RT	RT

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Microstructure

Results of image analysis obtained by Clemex Vision Lite program was given in Table 3. As seen in the table; % nodularity, nodule count, nodule size, graphite, ferrite and pearlite volume ratio values are close to that of values in GGG80 cast iron standard. It has shown that the method was implemented in camshaft production was correct and reliable.

Table 3. Microstructural analysis results

Nodularity (%)	Nodule count (mm ²)	Size of nodule (mμ)	Graphite Volume (%)	Ferrite volume (%)	Pearlite Volume (%)
90	299	12,15	9,13	26,27	64,60

Camshaft microstructure was given in Figure 3, the microstructure is a typical graphite cast iron casting structure. The ductile graphite nodules contain ferrite converted particles, which are carbonized around the graphite nodules, and a pearlitic matrix outside them. Increasing the number of graphite spheres increases the ferrite volume ratio and it is called bulls eye that it is seen ferrite structures close to generally graphite spheres and pearlite are seen in other parts.

Figure 3. The microstructure of the cast camshaft; a) 100X, b) 500X

The changes in the microstructure due to the austempering time and the quenching media were shown in Fig.4. In all the austempered samples, the microstructure was composed of austenite and unconverted austenite due to the time period of the process. As a result of 2% nital etching, Ferrite dark, high-carbon austenite light-colored and unconverted austenite appear as light-colored large areas. In the austempering heat treatment, the amount of ferrite and converted austenite increased while the amount of unconverted austenite decreased as the ferritin precipitated from the austenite, depending on the time required for diffusion. As the austempering period increased after the treatment interval, there was a decrease in the number of sphere (Fig. 4 e-g) and the sphere sizes increased accordingly. The changes in microstructure by air cooling and oil cooling after the austempering process are shown in Fig. 4 b-d-f-h. When these microstructures were examined, it was observed that the residual stresses increased.

Figure 4. Microstructures of austempered camshaft, 100X; a) 60 min. air cooled, b) 60 min. oil cooled, c) 120 min. air cooled, d) 120 min. oil cooled, e) 180 min. air cooled, f) 180 min. oil cooled, g) 240 min. air cooled, h) 240 min. oil cooled

3.2. Mechanical Tests

3.2.1. Hardness Results

Because the core of camshaft cools more slowly than that of surface, it is softer and measured with Brinell hardness. The changes in the hardness of the samples depending on the casting conditions, austempering time and the different quenching media are given in Table 4. Hardness values are observed depending on the amount of perlite in the phase structure in the samples in the spilled condition. As a result of the austempering heat treatment, an increase in hardness values was observed. This is due to the increase in amount of C that the matrix austenite solves. It is seen that there are not very large differences between the hardness values of the austempered samples. Hardness values of the austempered and oil-cooled specimens are higher than those of the air-cooled specimens. In parallel with the increase in the austempering period, the hardness values of all samples decreased.

Table 4. Hardness analysis results (HB)

Quenching Media	As Cast	60 min. Aus.	120 min. Aus.	240 min. Aus.	360 min. Aus.
cooling in air	227	421	479	401	375
cooling in oil		459	532	441	393

3.2.2. Tensile Test Results

Tensile tests were conducted three times for each sample and average values of tensile properties were calculated and submitted. Tensile test results were given in Table 5. As can be seen from the results, tensile strengths were observed according to the amount of perlite in the phase structure of the samples in the spilled condition. As a result of the austempering heat treatment, an increase in tensile strength values was observed. As the austempering period increases after the austempering process interval, tensile and yield strengths decrease and % elongation increases. The tensile strengths of air cooled specimens are higher than those of oil-cooled specimens. The highest tensile strength was observed for 120 min. austempered and air cooled samples.

Table 5. Tensile test results

Quenching Media	Tensile Properties	As Cast	60 min. Aus.	120 min. Aus.	240 min. Aus.	360 min. Aus.
cooling in air	Yield strength (MPa)	473,65	529,47	640,98	561,54	537,69
	Tensile strength (MPa)	744,12	1125,63	1518,34	1398,21	1250,26
	% Elongation (%)	6,18	3,23	2,16	2,85	3,14
cooling in oil	Yield strength (MPa)	-	516,65	548,73	533,31	506,44
	Tensile strength (MPa)	-	1014,4	1409,78	1212,52	1059,71
	% Elongation (%)	-	3,72	2,33	3,2	3,47

3.2.2.1. Fracture Surfaces SEM Analysis

General fracture surface of the samples in the casting condition are seen in the figure 5. It exhibits a rather flat and roughness-free fracture character with no porosity formation / accumulation. A mixed fracture mode occurs with ductile and brittle property. Detailed surface fracture is seen in Figure 5b that was taken from a centrally indented area. Ductile fracture (A) is observed in some regions close to the nodules, and cleavage-like "quasi-cleavage" brittle fracture is observed in the other large sections.

Figure 5. SEM analyzes of fracture surfaces of tensile samples in casting conditions; a) general fracture surface view, b) detail fracture cross section views from the central region

The general fracture figure of the sample austempered and cooled in air at 120 minutes was given in Figure 6. The vacuum/pore region takes place on the left side in the Figure 6a. On the upper right, there is darkening due to charge effect and scattering and it is not related with the sample. Figure 6b shows the fracture surface data was obtained in the central region. In the figures occurred by mixed fracture mode, ductile fracture was observed in regions indicated by "A", and cleavage-like fracture was observed in regions indicated by "B".

Figure 6. SEM analyzes of fracture surfaces of 120 min. austempered and different quenched media tensile samples; a) general fracture surface view, b) detail fracture cross section views from the central region

3.2.3. Wear Test Results

Three tests were conducted for 10N and 30N load and their average was calculated given. Wear test results were shown in Table 6. As can be seen from the results, perlite formation in spilled condition increases the hardness value and accordingly the amount of wear is reduced. The amount of abrasion according to the casting conditions decrease by increasing the hardness value of all the austempered camshaft samples. Since the hardness values in the oil cooling process are higher than those in air cooling, wear loss is less. The lowest wear amount of wear was determined at 120 minute austempered and oil cooled camshaft specimens under load of 10N. The highest amount of wear in the ball bearing that was used as abrasive was achieved with the abrasion of the camshaft samples in the casting condition under load of 30N. Because the highest coefficient of friction is obtained in this test. Therefore, as the coefficient of friction increases, the amount of wear increases.

Table 6. Wear test results

Quenching Media	Load (N)	Wear Properties	As Cast	60 min. Aus.	120 min. Aus.	240 min. Aus.	360 min. Aus.
cooling in air	10	Loss of Sample (mg)	1,1123	0,5665	0,4431	0,5921	0,6618
		Friction Coefficient	0,6932	0,321	0,2928	0,3471	0,403
	30	Loss of Sample (mg)	3,9422	1,7503	1,2125	1,8252	1,9394
		Friction Coefficient	0,8212	0,5215	0,4236	0,5421	0,5832
cooling in oil	10	Loss of Sample (mg)	-	0,4452	0,3827	0,4935	0,5152
		Friction Coefficient	-	0,2947	0,2671	0,3211	0,3337
	30	Loss of Sample (mg)	-	1,1337	0,9191	1,1227	1,2985
		Friction Coefficient	-	0,4985	0,4037	0,5236	0,5597

3.2.3.1. Wear Surfaces SEM Analysis

General wear surfaces of the samples in the cast condition were seen in Figure 7. When Figure 7a was examined that there is an adhesive wear mechanism under 10N load and abrasive wear is seen with increase in load (Figure 7b).

Figure 7. SEM analyzes of wear surfaces of wear samples in casting conditions; a) 10N b) 30N

The general wear image of the austempered and oil-cooled sample at 120 minutes is given in Fig 8. When Figure 8 is examined, abrasive wear is seen.

Figure 8. SEM analyzes of wear surfaces of 120 min. austempered and different quenched media wear samples; a) 10N, b) 30N

4. Conclusions

In this study, the effect of the austempering treatment applied on ductile graphite cast iron with different quenching media microstructure, hardness, tensile strength, wear resistance were investigated and following results were obtained;

1. When microstructure of samples in the camshaft under casting conditions contain graphite nodules and ferritic-pearlitic matrix structure, austempered camshaft samples microstructure contains ausferrite (austenite + ferrite) microstructure.
2. As the austempering time period increases, the amount of untransformed austenite decreases while the amount of ferrite and high-carbon austenite increases in general.
3. As the austempering period increases, the size of the sphere increases as the number of sphere per unit area decreases.
4. Austempering process applied on GGG80 class nodular cast iron, the core hardness value of nodular cast iron has increased from 227HB to 459HB.
5. When tensile strength of camshaft with as cast is compared with that of austempered cast iron has 105% higher tensile strength than the camshaft with as-cast. The maximum tensile strength was obtained from the camshaft having air cooled austenitized at 260°C and 120 min. similar results were obtained for yield strength. However, the % elongation is decreased by austempering heat treatment.

6. When the wear samples are examined, it is seen the mechanism of adhesive wear under load of 10N. A 360% increase in abrasion resistance was observed due. Abrasive wear mechanism is seen with increasing load.

7. After the austempering process, the camshaft samples are cooled by air and oil cooling. When the samples cooled in oil were examined, it was observed that the residual stresses increased.

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